

Interaction of Benzoyl Isothiocyanate and Primary and Secondary Amines: Formation of the Related Benzoylthiocarbamides and Thiocarbamides

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The interaction of benzoyl isothiocyanate and certain primary and secondary amines, leading to the formation of the corresponding 1-substituted- and 1,1-disubstituted-3-benzoylthiocarbamides, and the hydrolysis of the latter to the related thiocarbamides have been described. The reaction is of general preparatory value for thiocarbamides which are otherwise more difficultly obtained.

Benzoyl isothiocyanate is known to condense with amines¹, alcohols^{2a}, amino-acids², hydrazines³, phenols⁴, and thiols⁴. With aromatic primary amines, Douglas and Dains⁵ observed the formation of the related 1-aryl-3-benzoylthiocarbamides which on hydrolysis afforded in good yields the corresponding 1-arylthiocarbamides. Their procedure has been adapted by Frank and Smith³ as a preparatory method for phenylthiocarbamide. Undoubtedly, a better and more economical method for the preparation of 1-arylthiocarbamides consists in the isomeric change of the related amine-thiocyanates which need not be isolated pure⁶. But this latter procedure cannot be applied for the preparation of 1-alkylthiocarbamides^{7a-c} and only with limited success in the case of 1,1-disubstituted thiocarbamides. Compounds of both these categories have to be prepared through the related isothiocyanates or the cyanamides which are not readily available and are expensive.

The reaction of benzoyl isothiocyanate has therefore now been investigated with some aromatic and aliphatic primary and secondary amines and mixed secondary amines. In all cases, the expected 1-substituted-3-benzoylthiocarbamides were obtained, a study of the hydrolysis of which was carried out with a view to assessing their usefulness for preparing the 1-substituted and 1,1-disubstituted thiocarbamides. The yields of the benzoyl derivatives averaged around 90% excepting in the cases of methyl, ethyl, propyl⁸, and dimethyl amines, where these were 65, 70, 75, and 52% respectively. These, excepting the

- (a) Miquel, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1877, v, 11, 295.
(b) Dixon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1889, 55, 305, 622.
(c) Dixon and Taylor, *ibid.*, 1906, 93, 692.
(d) *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 54, 1408.
- Elmore *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 1141.
- Hoggarth, *ibid.*, 1949, 1160.
- Elmore *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1950, 4456.
- Frank and Smith, *Org. Syntheses*, 1948, 28, 89-91.
- Krall and Gupta, *this Journal*, 1935, 12, 629.
- (a) Sahaarabudhey and Singh, *ibid.*, 1953, 29, 499.
(b) Singh and Salkia, *ibid.*, 1953, 29, 695.
(c) Sahaarabudhey and Singh, *ibid.*, 1954, 31, 628.

1,1-dimethyl- and 1,1-diethyl-3-benzoylthiocarbamides, were found more or less easily hydrolysable by alkali and under suitable conditions the yields of the related thiocarbamides ranged between 85 and 95%. The 1,1-dimethyl- and 1,1-diethyl-3-benzoylthiocarbamides were found indifferent to hydrolysis by dilute acid or alkali. Strong alkali, however, decomposed them completely.

It is clear from these results that not only 1-phenylthiocarbamide⁵ or other 1-arylthiocarbamides, but many other 1-substituted and 1,1-disubstituted thiocarbamides can be successfully prepared through this reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Substituted and 1,1-disubstituted 3-benzoylthiocarbamides were obtained by the procedure of Frank and Smith³. The compounds were crystallised in all cases from ethanol. The results of these experiments are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

1-Substituted 3-benzoylthiocarbamides.

S. No.	Amine used.	*Product.	Yield.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
1	<i>o</i> -Toluidine (6.7 g.)	1- <i>o</i> -Tolyl-3-benzoyl T ^b (13.5 g.)	95%	117°	..	..
2	<i>p</i> -Toluidine (6.7 g.)	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-3-benzoyl T ^b (13.8 g.)	97	157°	..	..
3	<i>o</i> -Phenetidine (7.4 g.)	1- <i>o</i> -Phenetyl-3-benzoyl T (14.0 g.)	91	119°	N: 9.00	9.33
4	<i>p</i> -Phenetidine (7.4 g.)	1- <i>p</i> -Phenetyl-3-benzoyl T (13.9 g.)	90	152°	N: 9.16	9.33
5	α -Naphthylamine (7.7 g.)	1- α -Naphthyl- (13.8 g.)	80	171°	N: 8.90	9.15
6	β -Naphthylamine (7.7 g.)	1- β -Naphthyl- (14.4 g.)	94	173°	N: 8.88	9.15
7	2-Aminopyridine (4.9 g.)	1-(2-Pyridyl)- (11.9 g.)	85	144°	S: 12.18	12.1
8	<i>N</i> -Methylaniline (6.7 g.)	1-1-Methylphenyl- (13.0 g.)	92	137°	N: 10.25	10.37
9	<i>N</i> -Ethylaniline (6.9 g.)	1, 1-Ethylphenyl- ^{1b} , (13.0 g.)	90	123°		
10	Diphenylamine (10.8 g.)	1, 1-Diphenyl- ^{1c} (17.0 g.)	85	125°		

5. Miquel, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1877, **v.** 11, 316, 324.

TABLE I (contd.)

S. No.	Amine used.	Product*	Yield.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
11	Methylamine (2.1 g.)	1-Methyl-3-benzoyl-T ⁹ (6.9 g.)	65	150°		
12	Ethylamine (2.6 g.)	1-Ethyl. ⁸ " " (8.5 g.)	70	133°		
13	Propyl n-amino (3.5 g.)	1-n-Propyl. ⁸ " " (10.8 g.) " "	75	133°	N: 12.3	12.6
14	Benzylamine (7.0 g.)	1-Benzyl. ⁸ " " (14.5 g.)	90	143°		
15	Dimethylamine (2.6 g.)	1, 1-Dimethyl- " " (6.8 g.)	52	117°	N: 13.5	13.75
16	Diethylamine (4.9 g.)	1, 1-Diethyl. ¹⁰ " " (13.0 g.)	92	101°		

T stands for thiocarbamide.

* Identification by mixed m.p., comparison with m.p. reported earlier or by analysis, as the case may be.

Hydrolysis of Benzoylthiocarbamides.—The hydrolysis of 1-aryl-3-benzoylthiocarbamides was carried out by boiling with 10% aqueous NaOH solution for 5 to 10 minutes⁹. The hydrolysate on cooling and acidification deposited a mixture of the expected 1-arylthiocarbamide and benzoic acid. The latter was redissolved by just basification of the mixture with dilute ammonia and the insoluble residue of 1-arylthiocarbamide was filtered; yield was about 90%.

Like the preceding thiocarbamides, the 1,1-diaryl- or alkylaryl-3-benzoylthiocarbamides could not be successfully hydrolysed by strong aqueous alkali. The hydrolysis was far too slow; consequently, the resulting thiocarbamides were found to decompose. Prolonged (4 to 6 hrs.) hydrolysis with dilute (2%) refluxing ethanolic alkali (15ml/1 g.) carried out in 2 to 3 stages proved successful. In the case of 1,1-diphenyl-3-benzoylthiocarbamide, the 1,1-diphenylthiocarbamide, which crystallised on cooling after 3 hours' refluxing, was collected and the filtrate subjected to further refluxing. In other cases, where the thiocarbamide remained in solution, after 2 hours' refluxing the hydrolysate was cooled and made slightly acidic, when the unchanged benzoyl derivative and benzoic acid separating were filtered. The filtrate on just neutralisation, evaporation of ethanol, and dilution precipitated the thiocarbamide. The unchanged benzoyl derivative, washed with very dilute alkali to remove the admixed benzoic acid, was subjected to further hydrolysis and again worked up as above after 2 hours and the process repeated a third time. The total yield of the thiocarbamides in all cases was found to be 85 to 90% with respect to the amount of benzoyl derivative hydrolysed. Only very small quantities of the benzoyl derivative remained unchanged after a three-stage hydrolysis.

1-Alkyl-3-benzoylthiocarbamides could be hydrolysed quantitatively by boiling with calculated quantity of an ethanolic alkali solution (2%) for 2 hours. The resulting hydrolysate on acidification with dilute acid precipitated the benzoic acid which was removed by filtration. The filtrate on neutralisation was evaporated to dryness on a water bath and the residue extracted with pure dry acetone, when the expected thiocarbamide dissolved and could be recovered by distilling the acetone.

9. Dixon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 75, 383.

10. *Idem, ibid.*, 1926, 69, 603.

In the case of 1-benzyl-3-benzoylthiocarbamide, quantitative hydrolysis was achieved easily by boiling with dilute (5%) ethanolic alkali (10 ml/1 g.) for 30 minutes. The solution on cooling deposited crystals of pure benzylthiocarbamide. Results of these experiments are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Hydrolysis of 1-substituted-3-benzoylthiocarbamides

S. No.	Benzoylthiocarbamide hydrolysed (10 g.).	1-Substituted thiocarbamide formed.	Yield.	*M.P.
1	1-o-Tolyl- BT	1-o-Tolyl T. (5.5 g.)	90%	160°
2	1-p-Tolyl- ..	1-p-Tolyl T. (5.5 g.)	90	175°
3	1-o-Phenetyl- ..	1-o-Phenetyl T. (6.3 g.)	90	110°
4	1-p-Phenetyl- ..	1-p-Phenetyl T. (6.2 g.)	89	172°
5	1- α -Naphthyl- ..	1- α -Naphthyl T. (6.1 g.)	88	196°
6	1- β -Naphthyl- ..	1- β -Naphthyl T. (6.4 g.)	92	196°
7	1-(2-Pyridyl)- ..	1-(2-Pyridyl) T. (5.2 g.)**	87	151°
8	1, 1-Methylphenyl- ..	1, 1-Methylphenyl T. (5.1 g.)	85	106°
9	1, 1-Ethylphenyl- ..	1, 1-Ethylphenyl T. (5.4 g.)	86	110°
10	1,1-Diphenyl- ..	1, 1-Diphenyl T. (5.9 g.)	89	213°
11	1-Methyl- ..	1-Methyl T. (4.4 g.)	90	106°
12	1-Ethyl- ..	1-Ethyl T. (4.5 g.)	93	106°
13	1-n-Propyl- ..	1-n-Propyl T. (4.6 g.)	90	106°
14	1-Benzyl- ..	1-Benzyl T. (5.8 g.)	95	165°

BT stands for 3-benzoylthiocarbamide. T stands for thiocarbamide.

* In all cases the m.p.s agreed with authentic m.p.s.

**Identified by its reactions and analysis (Found: S, 21.06. C₆H₇N₂S requires S, 20.91)

Attempts to Hydrolyse 1,1-Diethyl- and 1,1-Dimethyl-3-benzoylthiocarbamides.—These thiocarbamides remained practically unaffected by boiling with the calculated quantity of dilute alkali. When concentrated solutions of alkali were used, these decomposed and only traces of the expected thiocarbamides could be obtained. The benzoyl derivatives were also found to decompose by boiling with dilute (3*N*) sulphuric acid. Attempts were also made to debenzoylate these by boiling with anilino and thiocarbamide, but without success.

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